

Projekt 72: Reengineering of Tietgen Kollegiet

In order to have a design that accounted for every environmental impact, the team used the Environmental Improvement Through Product Development guide. Therefore the majority of the study was focused on the reduction of impacts in that area. A concepts was generated, one where the majority of the focus was set on the simplification of the architecture and the enhancement of the indoor environment. The other proposed an new architectural solution, together with an improvement of the indoor environment. Study for the energy impact with BSim, and the daylight quality using Ecotect has been assessed. The final solution include both a new architectural solution, new building elements, and ventilation system that would ventilate every room in the building, which was not present in the current design.